

Trophic Cascades and Biodiversity in Terrestrial Ecosystems

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Abstract

The populations of different species in each trophic level of an ecosystem are an important parameter of that ecosystem. These populations help us to understand how long the ecosystem can survive, how many different species it can support within it and how stable it can remain during environmental stresses. The system itself needs to come up with ways to control the populations of its entire species and the populations in each trophic level need to be kept in check. Trophic cascades as powerful indirect interactions are one of the several mechanisms that can control entire ecosystems or biodiversity of the system. A trophic cascade is an ecological phenomenon that results from changes in the animals or plants at one or more levels of the food chain and is sparked by the presence or absence of apex predators. Trophic cascades occur in many ecosystems, and seem to be helpful in management, restoration and conservation of ecosystems. The factors regulating them are still incomprehensible, suggesting that the different hypotheses developed by various scholars of the community ecology have to be consolidated to clearly understand and explain the mechanisms of trophic cascades. The data from reviews highlight the influence of cascades specifically on structure of terrestrial ecosystems and establish it as an important constituent of native biodiversity.

Keywords

Trophic Cascade, Biodiversity Conservation, Terrestrial Ecosystems.

Introduction

Trophic cascades are powerful indirect interactions that can control entire ecosystems and generally occur when the impact of a predator on its prey's ecology drops down one more feeding level and affects the density and/or behavior of the prey's prey (Silliman & Angelini, 2012). Ecologists term this interaction as feeding, or trophic cascade wherein predators limit the density and/or behaviour of their prey and thereby enhance survival of the next lower trophic level. If the population of one species in a trophic level rises too much, or falls drastically, then intense competition and prevention of energy transfer may result in ecosystem collapse. Therefore, for a stable and diversified ecosystem the populations in each trophic level need to be kept in check. System itself comes up with various ways to control the populations of its entire species and make sure it remains in the most suitable range. Many researchers have documented that in certain life stages the behavioural response of prey can have a strong indirect impact on terrestrial food chain interactions that can be interpreted as trophic cascade.

Ripple et al. (2016) define trophic cascades as "the indirect species interactions that originate with the predators and spread downward through food webs". It may operate in both directions 'top-down' as well as 'bottom-up' depending on which of the two, the predator or producer, is present in lesser numbers (or biomass). In addition to their direct top down effects on primary producers, trophic cascades also generate 'knock-on' effects. Together, they indirectly influence diverse ecosystem processes such as wildfires, diseases, carbon sequestration and biodiversity. For this reason, ecologists emphasize the need to monitor and assess trophic downgrading impacts in managing wildlife, fisheries and other natural resources (T Ramakrishna Rao 2018). Recent studies have shown that occurrences of trophic cascades in terrestrial ecosystems are not as rare as they were thought to be earlier. In fact, there are now many documented cases of trophic cascades in all the major biomes of the world.

Objective of study

Trophic cascades have been the subject matter for substantial research regarding environment conservation during the last decade. This paper aims to review and discuss

how trophic cascades control the different populations in the terrestrial communities to maintain their biodiversity.

Review of Literature

The term 'trophic cascade' was first used by Paine, and the concept was proposed by Hairston et al. in 1960 as tri-trophic Green World Hypothesis (GWH). Later Fretwell (1987) and Oksanen et al. (1981) generalized it to systems of one to five trophic levels – the Exploitative Ecosystem Hypothesis (EEH). Pace et al. (1999) further suggested that trophic cascades are widespread, although the factors regulating them are still incomprehensible. Hairston and his coworkers (1960) were of the view that the world is green because abundance of herbivores is controlled by higher trophic levels. They also suggested that grazers are not limited by food on earth but limited instead by predators that keep their populations and negative impacts on plants in check.

Trophic cascades have been observed in many kinds of systems. However as predicted by the GWH and EEH, trophic cascades are not a universal phenomenon in terrestrial habitats (Polis 1999, Strong 1992, Polis and Strong 1996). As it is implausible to simplify communities composed of complex food webs into simple food chains and imply 'strong interactions within food webs to describe trophic cascades. Polis (1999) recently suggested species-level and community-level cascades to elucidate the type of cascade phenomenon occurring in the terrestrial systems. In 'Species-level cascades' changes in predator numbers affect the success of a subset (one or a few) of the community or compartment of a food web. 'Community-level cascades basically are known to alter or affect total primary producer biomass/density throughout an entire system, in accordance with the GWH and EEH.

All cascades in terrestrial systems studied by Schmitz et al. (2000) showed interactions within subsets of a community. The lack of indubitable evidence for community-wide trophic cascades from terrestrial systems may be either due to the absence of appropriately scaled experiments involving mammal herbivores or that community-wide trophic cascades are rare in terrestrial systems. Community-wide effects of trophic cascades are demonstrated only in aquatic systems. Recent conceptual and heuristic studies suggested that aquatic systems are more suitable for GWH and EEH models. They are more likely to possess characteristics that fit with the simplifying assumptions of these theoretical models. Despite the presence of a variety of evidence accumulated to suggest a strong role of consumers' effects and trophic cascades in the terrestrial ecosystems, most of them argue to represent species level trophic cascades (Tadesse SA, 2017).

All natural systems deviate from the simplifying assumptions of the GWH and EEH; they tend to depart from clear community-level trophic cascades except the terrestrial agricultural systems. Recent theoretical work of (McCann and Hastings 1997, McCann et.al. 1998) suggests that most terrestrial systems are much more complex and complex systems are more stable than less diverse systems. As high diversity systems have significantly more redundancy and it limits the strength of trophic cascades (Leibold 1997). Terrestrial food webs form trophic triangles instead of linear trophic chains of aquatic systems, so the top down effect tends to dissipate through their trophic network and becomes difficult to detect unlike in the aquatic food webs (T Ramakrishna Rao 2018). Ripple et.al. (2024) examined the relationship between climate change and trophic cascades as to know how changes in climate can influence the trajectory and intensity of the mechanism involved in trophic cascade.

Terrestrial systems represent species level trophic cascades and are therefore related with the diversity of the systems. It can be exploited for biodiversity conservation through improvement, restoration or replacement of required species.

Methodology The study is based on secondary data which have been collected from various books, research papers from different national and international journals, review articles, general articles, websites etc.

Analysis

Models For Understanding Trophic Cascade

The GWH model (Fig1) proposed by Hairston et.al. (1960) elucidated that some parts of the world have remained green primarily because herbivores are held in check by their enemies and also don't consume a large fraction of indigestible plant biomass. Fretwell-Oksanen's EEH model (Fig 2.) explain that differing productivity, herbivory, and predation makes the habitat green in systems with odd (1 or 3) trophic levels, but desolate in systems with even (2 or 4) levels (Oksanen and Fretwell 1981)

Fig 1: GWH Model - the trophic control hypothesis (usually referred to as 'the green world hypothesis').

Fig 2: Fretwell-Oksanen Exploitation Ecosystem Hypothesis Model

The Fretwell-Oksanen's EEH model also predicts that top-down control should be in one trophic level but bottom-up control in three trophic levels. The number of trophic levels, and top-down or bottom-up control is a function of the magnitude of productivity of the terrestrial ecosystem (Oksanen 1981). Recent studies show that in many ecosystems, both top-down and bottom-up factors might be operating simultaneously (T Ramakrishna Rao 2018). Both HSS (Hariston et.al. 1960) and Menge and Sutherland (1987) models predict that predator removal will strongly affect herbivore numbers. Herbivores depress plants; predators depress herbivores; predators thus indirectly facilitate plants through their cascading effects (Oksanen and Fretwell 1981, Ripple and Beschta 2003, 2004, Chase 2003, Estes and Duggin 1995).

This would lead to having a controlling mechanism either top-down or bottom-up to keep the balance of the biotic communities in the terrestrial ecosystems. Decomposers are controlled by the litters a trophic level below them. There is no trophic level above them and it does not seem that the climate can control them. (Hairston et.al.1960, Oksanen and Fretwell 1981, Ayal Y. 2010, Estes and Duggin 1995).

Theoretical models such as GWH and EEH suggested that both resources and predators interact to structure the natural food webs and thereby reduce the impacts of herbivory on green plants in the terrestrial ecosystems. (Hairston et.al. 1960, Oksanen and Fretwell 1981). However, consumers that exert strong cascading effects within a particular plant-herbivore food chain are almost always deeply subsidized by resources from many sources outside the focal chain (Polis 1999, Hartley and Jones 2004).

Trophic Cascade In The Tropical Rainforest, Grassland And Desert Ecosystem:

The facts reveal that trophic cascade and population control works differently in different types of terrestrial ecosystems. Species diversities at various trophic levels make the control of biotic communities' complex in the tropical rainforest ecosystem. Thus, they lack clear trophic levels especially among predators and have potential for high inter-trophic level interactions both along and across food webs (Ayal 1998, 2010).The grassland ecosystem supports a large number of herbivores whose population is largely

checked and regulated by predators (Hartley and Jones 2004). Grassland ecosystem is more productive compared to the desert ecosystem. Thus, the cascading effect of top predators on plant communities in the grassland ecosystem is strong (Chase 2003). Moreover, both biotic and abiotic factors work together to shape and control the size and the structure of the grassland communities (Ayal 1998, 2010).

Therefore, herbivores population control and the cascading effect of predators on plants in tropical rainforests seem to be a bit more complex compared with grassland or the desert ecosystem.

Example of Trophic Cascade in Terrestrial System:

Tropical Rainforests (Terborgh et al. 2001)

John Terborgh and his colleagues compared the abundance of predators of invertebrates (birds, lizards, anurans, and spiders), seed predators (rodents), and herbivores (howler monkeys, iguanas, and leaf-cutter ants) in manmade impoundment of islands in the midst of a Venezuelan rainforest with and without vertebrate predators to assess the potential for a trophic cascade. They found an abundance of seed predators and herbivores, and a decrease in growth of seedlings and saplings of canopy-forming trees on predator-free islands. This example shows that even in tropical rainforests with complex food webs and high primary productivity, trophic cascades represented by the removal of top-down regulation can induce a rapid fall in the stability and structure of biological communities.

Yellowstone National Park (Ripple & Larson 2000)

A Classic example for the impacts of predators on ecosystems and biodiversity has been observed from Yellowstone National Park located in western United States (Fig 3). After the elimination of wolves *Canis Lupus* from the park during the 1880s-1920s elk *Cervus elaphus* fed extensively throughout the different habitats in the park. This resulted in the loss of aspen *Populus tremuloides*, cottonwoods *Populus deltoides* and willows *Salix* spp and has been correlatively linked with the extirpation of grey wolves. Study revealed that when wolves were reintroduced in 1995, they started to have the most remarkable offense. It was observed that elk avoid 'risky' areas with high densities of grey wolves and spend more time in alternate habitats where wolf densities are lower, It resulted in lowering the local browsing pressure in high-risk foraging areas on aspen suckers in high-risk foraging areas (Fortin et al. 2005).

The study also suggested that the reintroduction of the wolves has not only benefited the trees, but also cascaded to bird species and beavers. In order to grow *Castor canadensis*, which needed huge forests, these regions are currently being dammed, reintroducing wetlands to the park. The wolves even changed the behaviour of the river, woodlands started establishing in these areas. Wolves' small numbers not only transformed the ecosystem of the park but also its physical geography. Just one top predator can produce so much impact on the ecosystem and this is what is known as trophic cascade.

Kauffmann et al. (2010) challenged the wolf led trophic cascade and other findings also suggest that behaviorally-mediated trophic cascade may affect growth and survival of aspens by changing the foraging patterns of elk.

Fig 3 -Source -
<https://esajournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1890/04-1269>

Salt Marshes (Silliman et al. 2005)

Among the most prolific ecosystems on Earth, salt marshes are researched as the model for bottom-up managed systems. According to Silliman et al. (2005), blue crabs can be used in experiments to manipulate consumers in order to influence the distribution and quantity of the most common snails. Long believed to be a detritivore expert, the snail actually regulates marsh plant growth by cultivating fungus on living plant tissue. The purpose of this recently discovered trophic cascade is to prevent marshes from turning into mudflats. Snail populations have risen and mowed down marshes, creating a patchwork of vegetated and bare mudflat sections when blue crab levels have decreased as a result of drought stress.

Findings Traditional trophic level management practices are viewed as predominantly bottom-up in nature (Estes & Peterson). Temperate and tropical forests, kelp beds, grasslands, and salt marsh communities, have long been viewed as classic examples of bottom-up regulated systems and top-down effects in management and conservation efforts have been generally neglected for over half of a century. Combined findings of various studies reveal that bottom-up and top-down forces are both key determinants of the key plant community. Ecologists should identify, integrate and evaluate their understanding of top-down controlling effects on management and conservation of plant communities and incorporate them into their conservation plans.

Conclusion Trophic cascades are potent interactions that tightly control ecosystem function and biodiversity. Compared to aquatic ecosystems, terrestrial communities are more functionally diverse and complex. Trophic cascades were first believed to be uncommon, but we now know that they may be found in a variety of ecosystems, including those with vascular plant assemblages, which were previously believed to be immune to consumer control. Trophic cascades have been observed in Open Ocean and tropical woods, according to recent investigations. These discoveries have improved and deepened our understanding of the factors that encourage and restrict the emergence and spread of predatory effects. Thus, taking into account scale-dependence generally and CSIs (cross-scale interactions) specifically could improve our comprehension of trophic cascades (Donadi et.al.2017). However, humans also affect trophic cascades, so "trophic cascades" of new are not similar to "trophic cascades of old" (Polis et.al. 2000). According to Strong (1992), trophic cascades are generally thought to be more significant in aquatic than in terrestrial systems, simple than in complex food webs, homogeneous than in heterogeneous systems, communities predominated by nonvascular plants (i.e. algae), and systems where unappealing plants don't replace those that have been overgrazed. The relationship between trophic cascades and climate change was then examined by Ripple et.al.(2024), outlining the ways in which trophic cascades might be used to enhance climate resilience and, on the other hand, how climate change can cause or influence trophic cascades' intensity and trajectory. For a better understanding of the significance of trophic cascades in ecosystem restoration, more research is required. In order to comprehend and explain the mechanisms of trophic cascades, this review paper concluded that the many ideas generated by various community ecology experts needed to be combined.

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